

THE EFFECT OF FIBER STRENGTH, MATRIX AND INTERPHASE PROPERTY ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MULTI-AXIAL WARP KNITTED FABRIC COMPOSITE

Kazuya ETO, Toshiko OSADA, Asami NAKAI, Hiroyuki HAMADA
Advanced Fibro science, Kyoto Institute of Technology
Yoshinobu TSUCHIYA
Shindo sennikogyo

ABSTRACT

In this study, the decrease in the strength of fiber bundle during textile process on multi-axial warp knitted fabric was investigated. Using two kinds of fiber bundles with different surface treatments, the decrease in the strength of fiber bundle during textile process and the effect of surface treatment on mechanical properties of composite were discussed. Moreover, considering these results, the hybrid knitted fabric was proposed, and the usefulness of interfacial hybrid was proved by tensile and bending tests.

Key words: multi-axial warp knitted fabric, hybrid composite, tensile strength, bending strength

INTRODUCTION

Multi-axial warp knitted fabric allows the placement of warp, weft, and off-axis materials directly into the fabric structure. Moreover, not only the unidirectional fiber bundles, but also chopped strand mat can be combined. One of the most attractive features of this fabric is the ability to combine multiple layers of oriented yarn in a single structure. The multi-axial warp knitted fabric composite with no crimps can possess higher mechanical properties and reduce the cost with omission of the stacking process. In addition, the multi-axial warp knitted fabric can be treated as a textile fabric with the good drapability.

During the textile process, filaments would be damaged by the friction between fiber bundle and machine and/or fiber bundle and fiber bundle, so that the decrease in the strength of fiber bundle was expected. Thus, fiber strength in the composites is not same as that in catalog supplied by fiber producing company. Therefore, it was urgently necessary to examine the decrease in the strength of fiber bundle by the friction during textile process on multi-axial warp knitted fabric. Besides, the effect of the decrease in the strength of fiber bundle on composite should be considered. In this paper, multi-axial warp knitted fabric was mentioned, however, this can be adopted to all of the textile proceed fabric.

Generally, there are two kinds of surface treatment on glass fiber bundle for textile fabric (Figure 1). One is the coupling agent and the other is the binding agent. The purpose of coupling agent is to improve the interfacial chemical adhesion between fiber and matrix. Binding agent was used for the purpose of decreasing in the friction between fibers during textile process. It had been known that the decrease in the strength of fiber bundle during textile process was restrained by using binding agent, but the much binder agent results in decrease in interfacial properties [ref.1].

In this study, in order to investigate the decrease in the strength of fiber bundle during textile process, tensile test of fiber bundles in virgin and undergoing the textile process was conducted. Two kinds of surface treatments on glass fiber bundle were used, and the effects of surface treatments and textile process on the decrease in the tensile strength of fiber bundle and mechanical properties of composite were investigated. Moreover, considering advantages of two kinds of surface treatments, the usefulness of interfacial hybrid on multi-axial warp knitted fabric was discussed. Here, interfacial hybrid means the use of two fiber bundles with different surface treatment in one knitted fabric.

THE DECREASE IN THE STRENGTH OF FIBER BUNDLE

Multi-axial warp glass knitted fabric was adopted, whose structure is that unidirectional fiber bundles are aligned in 0° and 90° directions (here, 0° and 90° direction is called L and T direction respectively in this study) and linked with knitted yarn (it is called L/T knitted fabric, Figure 2). On L/T knitted fabric, fiber bundle in L and T direction are knitted after through the different process: the fiber bundle passes different course and the number of contact point with parts of machine is different. Therefore, the fiber bundles were picked out from both L and T directions of L/T knitted fabric. The virgin fiber bundle not subjected to textile process was also used to be compared. Tensile test of these fiber bundles were conducted by using INSTRON universal testing machine (Type 4206) with cross head speed of 20mm/min. The number of sampling fiber bundle was over 20.

The strength of fiber bundle of virgin and after knitting and the damage ratio are shown in Table 1. Here, the damage ratio is shown in Equation (1). In the fiber bundle in L direction, the damage ratio was no more than 3.6%, on the other hand, the damage ratio of fiber bundle was 23.4% in the T direction process. As a result, in the L direction process, there was little damage by friction and the strength of fiber bundle could hardly decrease, while the strength of fiber bundle drastically decreased in the T direction process.

Figure 2 Schematic drawing of L/T knitted fabric

Table 1 The decrease in the fiber bundle during textile process

	Virgin fiber bundle strength (GPa)	Fiber bundle strength after knitting (GPa)	Damage ratio (%)
L direction	1.41	1.36	3.6
T direction	1.41	1.08	23.4

$$\text{Damage ratio} = \{1 - (\text{virgin fiber bundle strength})/(\text{fiber bundle strength after knitting})\} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

THE EFFECT OF SURFACE TREATMENTS ON FIBER AND COMPOSITE

The effects of surface treatment on decrease in the strength of fiber bundle during textile process were investigated. In this case, the tensile test of fiber bundle which was picked out only from T direction process was conducted, because it had been found that there was little damage by friction in the L direction. In this paper, two kinds of fiber bundle are called Type A and Type B respectively.

The strength of each fiber bundles of virgin and after knitting and the damage ratio are shown in Table 2. The strength of Type A decreased at 10.6% during textile process, on the other hand, the strength of Type B decreased at 16.9%. As a result, it was found that the fiber bundle of Type A had higher strength than that of Type B for friction between fiber bundle and knitting machine.

Next, unidirectional multi-axial warp knitted fabric which has only T direction fiber bundles was specially fabricated by using fiber bundles of Type A and Type B. In order to investigate the effect of surface treatment on composite, tensile and bending tests were conducted with the unidirectional

Table 2 The effect of surface treatments on fiber bundle in textile process

	Virgin fiber bundle strength (GPa)	Fiber bundle strength after knitting (GPa)	Damage ratio (%)
Type A	1.41	1.26	10.6
Type B	1.42	1.18	16.9

multi-axial warp knitted fabric composite. The specimens were fabricated by hand-lay-up with unsaturated polyester as matrix resin. The specimens were cut along 0° direction and 90° direction. Tensile test and bending test were conducted by INSTRON universal testing machine (Type 4206) with cross head speed of 1mm/min.

The tensile strength and bending strength are shown in Table 3 and Table 4. In both the tensile and bending tests in 0° direction, the strength of unidirectional composite with Type A was higher than that with Type B. On the contrary, in the 90° direction, the strength in unidirectional composite with Type B was higher than that of Type A. It was considered that the strength in 0° direction on unidirectional composites was considerably affected by the strength of fiber bundle, on the other hand, the strength in 90° direction was affected by adhesion property between fiber and matrix. Therefore, it was expected that Type B had higher adhesion properties than Type A. The strength of unidirectional composite with Type A was higher than that with Type B concerning both the tensile and bending tests of 0° direction, because the strength of Type A was higher than that of Type B as shown in Table 2. Moreover, failure aspect after bending test was observed for both types as shown in Figure 3. In the specimen of Type A, delamination was observed between layers, whereas the delamination was not seen in the specimen of Type B. Therefore, it was found from the result that Type A had high strength of fiber bundle for friction, however interfacial adhesion was lower. On the other hand, Type B had higher interfacial adhesion properties, but lower strength for friction.

Table 3 Results of tensile test in unidirectional multi-axial warp knitted fabric composite

Tensile strength	Type A	Type B
0 direction tensile strength(MPa)	641.5	591.9
90 direction tensile strength(MPa)	23.18	29.72

Table 4 Results of bending test in unidirectional multi-axial warp knitted fabric composite

Bending strength	Type A	Type B
0 direction bending strength(MPa)	999.7	959.6
90 direction bending strength(MPa)	44.63	48.43

Figure 3 (a) Fracture aspect after bending test in Type A

Figure 3 (b) Fracture aspect after bending test in Type B

HYBRID KNITTED FABRIC MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

From the above knowledge, hybrid L/T knitted fabric with Type A and Type B was proposed to develop both advantages. The hybrid L/T knitted fabric in which Type A was placed in L direction and Type B was placed in T direction was called Knit AB. In the same way, the hybrid L/T knitted fabric in which Type B was placed in L direction and Type A was placed in T direction was called Knit BA. Tensile and bending properties of hybrid L/T knitted fabric were investigated, and the usefulness of interfacial hybrid composite was examined.

The specimens for tensile test were fabricated by hand-lay-up. Unsaturated polyester was used as matrix resin. Then, the specimens were cut along L direction and T direction respect to longitudinal direction. Tensile test was conducted by using INSTRON universal testing machine (Type 4206) with cross head speed of 1mm/min. In order to compare hybrid L/T knitted fabric with conventional L/T knitted fabric, L/T knitted fabric composite which was fabricated only with Type A or Type B was called Knit A and Knit B respectively, and the tensile test was conducted similarly.

For the bending test, the specimens with 4 plies were fabricated by hand-lay-up with symmetrical stacking sequence. Then, specimens were cut along L direction and T direction in L/T knitted fabric, and 3-point bending test was conducted. Schematic drawings of each bending specimens are shown in Figure 4. Totally 8 type of specimen were prepared with 4 types of stacking sequence and 2 loading direction

Figure 4 Schematic drawings of specimens for bending test

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The results of tensile and bending tests are shown in Table 5 and Table 6. As shown in Table 5, the highest tensile strength in L direction was Knit AB, and the highest tensile strength in T direction was Knit BA. Schematic drawings of Knit AB and Knit BA which cut along L direction and T direction are shown in Figure 5. It was found from results of tensile test and Figure 4 that the highest tensile strength of hybrid L/T knitted fabric was resulted from the structure that Type A was placed in tensile direction and Type B was placed in transverse direction. Therefore, concerning tensile property, the usefulness of hybrid knitted fabric was proved.

Table 5 Results of tensile test in conventional and hybrid L/T knitted fabric

Tensile strength	Knit A	Knit B	Knit AB	Knit BA
L direction tensile strength(MPa)	345.0	337.6	349.1	338.8
T direction tensile strength(MPa)	335.1	324.3	295.4	348.9

Figure 5 Schematic drawings of specimens for tensile test in Knit AB and Knit BA

As shown in Table 6, the highest bending strength in L direction was Knit AB, and the highest bending strength in T direction was Knit BA. It was found from results of bending test and Figure 5 that high bending strength in L direction was achieved by L/T knitted fabric with placed Type A in longitudinal direction of specimen such as Knit A and Knit AB, because the bending strength was affected by the strength of fiber bundle. However, concerning the strength in L direction, the strength of Knit AB was much higher than that of Knit A although Knit A has Type A in longitudinal direction of specimen as same as Knit AB. Therefore, in order to investigate the difference in strength of Knit A and Knit AB, microscopic observation of failure aspect was conducted by in-situ observation during bending test with replica method.

Table 6 Results of bending test in conventional and hybrid L/T knitted fabric

Bending strength	Knit A	Knit B	Knit AB	Knit BA
L direction bending strength(MPa)	535.2	493.4	583.3	552.9
T direction bending strength(MPa)	483.7	402.9	422.2	536.6

Figure 6 shows microscopic failure aspects of Knit A, Knit B, Knit AB and Knit BA just before final failure. As shown Figure 6, transverse cracks progressed into third layer from tensile side on Knit A, on the other hand, transverse cracks hardly progressed on Knit B and Knit AB. Therefore, it is concluded that transverse crack was restrained by placing Type B in transverse direction. From these results, the reason of the highest bending strength of Knit AB in L direction was considered that higher strength of Type A and higher interface property of Type B were arranged in longitudinal and transverse direction respectively in Knit AB. As a consequence, concerning bending property, the usefulness of hybrid knitted fabric was also proved.

CONCLUSION

In the textile process of multi-axial warp knitted fabric, the fiber bundles were damaged by friction, and the strength of fiber bundle decreased. Moreover, it was found that protecting the fiber bundle from damage by friction with binding agent decreased interfacial adhesion properties between fiber and resin. On the contrary, the fiber bundle with higher interfacial adhesion was much damaged by friction. In addition, interfacial hybrid knitted fabric composite was proposed. The higher strength of hybrid knitted fabric composite was achieved compared with conventional knitted fabric.

REFERENCE

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Figure 6 (a) Microscopic failure aspect of bending test just before final failure in Knit A

Figure 6 (b) Microscopic failure aspect of bending test just before final failure in Knit B

